

THE ESSENCE OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TERMS DURING THE REFORMS IMPLEMENTED IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article describes the appearance of new pedagogical terms in the lexicon of the Uzbek language during the reforms implemented in the educational system of our Republic, the innovative lexemes found in the vocabulary of pedagogues as a result of the introduction of the Finnish educational system in the field of education, and as a result, the 4K educational model for textbooks the introduction of tasks based on.

Key words: 4K educational model, collaboration, communication, creative thinking, critical (critical) thinking, innovation, visual arts, metacognitive skills, innovation.

Introduction. The deepening of the process of development of Science in the world, the exchange of cultures, the introduction of newly created innovative technologies into the field of Science, the creation of a national curriculum based on advanced foreign experiences as a result, it gave rise to the development of new terminology in the field of linguistics. The result is the creation of new dictionaries in the pedagogical system, the development of national terminology. Dictionary units according to its semantic content, it can be classified into a group of terms with a single meaning and a multiple meaning. While a large amount of Uzbek lexicography is made up of monosyllabic lexicons, the nature of the special word – term, which serves to express the concept of a particular field, requires the same situation. However, the terminological principle ambiguous terms that serve to represent more than one concept contrary to the requirement are also observed in almost all field terminology. [1] Science as a result of these changes in education as it progresses from year to year, the active Dictionary of educators now includes a 4K educational model, collobarotsia, several new lexemes such as communicativity, critical thinking,

creative thinking, visual arts, metacognitive abilities, the "fincha standard of textbooks we can meet.

Main part. In the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "on additional measures for the further improvement of the educational system" [2] The Progressive experience of Finland in the field of Education of our country the task of introducing it into the system and the national curriculum was set. As a result of the introduction of this program, a number of new pedagogy related to the field of Education lexicographic concepts have entered. These concepts can be observed in the form of unambiguous or polysemy according to the meaning they represent. Uzbek language nothing that the phenomenon of synonymy is characteristic of its terminology, Q.Sapayev puts forward the idea that in the terminological system, synonymous terms occur primarily on the basis of the specific internal capabilities of the same language, and secondly, as a result of word acquisition from other languages or the penetration of dialectal words into the terminological System [3]. Linguist R.Shukurov, on the other hand, argues that the phenomena of polysemy and synonymy occur in the erminology of the Uzbek language, in particular, the phenomenon of synonymy in terminological systems, as well as lexical detailed pauses to different aspects of dubbing [4].

In the pedagogical terminology of linguistics, we can observe that the following units are recorded " " authoritarian technology – 1) Traditional Education is an expression of the process, a system based on the fact that in the process of teaching the student acts as an object, a teacher as a subject; 2) in the educational process, the student is taught management technology based on subordination. Method of teaching literature-1) a certain knowledge of students in the theory and methodology of literary education, educational science focused on the formation of skills, qualifications; 2) the methodology of teaching literature is the main field of private pedagogy. Course – 1) higher and secondary special education in their country, the period of study, stage (for example: first course, second course, etc.k.); 2) a completed statement of a certain scope of the field of Science and Science (for example: course system of Education). Pedagogical creativity-1) educational and educational tasks by the educator exceptional resolution at a high quality level. 2) enrichment of educational practice and theory. Pedagogical innovation-1) to pedagogical activity its the introduction of innovations in order to improve the effectiveness, changes in the content and technologies of Education; 2) new views and approaches to the educational process based on cultural traditions related to the process of developing the personality of a child in educational activities"[5]. What

does 4K mean? The 4K education model is a novel approach, starting with 4 letters “K” with their own name contains the principle. It is a national formed on the basis of the Finnish education system contains the principle.

CONCLUSION. In the system of serving lexemes, there are also cases of new acquisition of words in an active dictionary. Understanding the meaning of these terms, however, is important in the way that classes are passed in a qualitative and standard way.

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